
Status of Gulf Sturgeon *Acipenser oxyrinchus desotoi* in the Gulf of Mexico

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Abstract: Population viability of Gulf sturgeon (*Acipenser oxyrinchus desotoi*) a large, long-lived anadromous species designated as threatened under the US Endangered Species Act is currently uncertain. Historically Gulf sturgeon were found from Tampa Bay, Florida, to the Texas/Louisiana border. This species was extensively harvested in their eastern range (Florida) in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century but records from the western Gulf of Mexico (west of Mobile Bay) do not suggest large fisheries. Throughout the range of Gulf sturgeon, modifications to in-river and nearshore habitats such as dam construction, dredging, modifications to flow regimes and ongoing mortality threats from by-catch or boat strikes are thought to have contributed to population declines. These population declines ultimately led to regulatory closure of directed Gulf sturgeon fisheries and the species was granted protective listing status in the 1980s in different states and 1986 assigned to Gulf sturgeon in the 1980s. Research efforts on Gulf sturgeon have occurred throughout its distribution with the majority of research focused on basic population ecology including movement, growth, food habits, and population size estimation from tagging programs. We developed two types of population models using information from commercial landings and data from these previously conducted studies to develop an assessment of trends in Gulf sturgeon population abundance. We fit these models to data from the Apalachicola and Suwannee rivers from the western Gulf of Mexico. These rivers were chosen because of the availability of historical fishing records and long-term tagging data. Additionally, these two systems represent contrasting population abundances with the Apalachicola River supporting very small Gulf sturgeon populations (100-400 adults) and the Suwannee River thought to support the largest Gulf sturgeon population remaining in the Gulf of Mexico of 5000-7500 adult fish. We were interested in population abundance model performance between these two systems possibly large differences in abundance. We used a series of age-structured mark-recapture models (ASMR) to estimate abundance, recruitment, and mortality of Gulf sturgeon in the Apalachicola and Suwannee rivers, the two rivers that likely supported the largest fisheries. Key results for the Suwannee River demonstrate increasing trends in population size during the 1980s from about 2,500 age-2+ Gulf sturgeon to approximately 5,000 age-2+ individuals in the mid-1990s. However, trends in abundance since the late 1990s differ between model structure, with some models showing sharp population declines and others showing population increases. These differences are likely due to low recapture rates and sparse data. The Apalachicola River population has shown similar increasing patterns since the 1980s from 200 to 400 age-2+ Gulf sturgeon to 400-600 age-2+ Gulf sturgeon in the 1990s. Population estimates since 2000 differ between model structures assumed either showing a decline in recent years, or an increase in age-2+ Gulf sturgeon abundance to 600-1,000 individuals. Estimated natural mortality rate for the two populations also differ widely from about 5 to 7% annually in the Apalachicola River to 10-21% in the Suwannee River. A key result of our research is a demonstration of large uncertainty in population trajectories since the late 1990s, concurrent with changes in the monitoring programs, depending on model structure is used. We also used a stock reduction analysis (SRA)

to reconstruct historical population biomass prior to the onset of commercial fishing. Our results suggest that population biomass for this species in Florida was severely reduced by about 90% during a short, but intense, period of commercial harvest. After large-scale fishing was abandoned, a small (exploitation less than 5% annually), but sustainable, fishery persisted until the fishery was closed in 1984. Assessing Gulf sturgeon population status is difficult due to a combination of life history characteristics (skip spawning where individuals do not return to spawn each year), behavior (gear avoidance), and variations in sampling programs (effort and location) that all contribute to uncertainty in current population estimates. This highlights key uncertainties in available data for assessing status and trends in Gulf sturgeon populations. This uncertainty could lead to divergent management policies related to this listed species.

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INTRODUCTION

The Gulf of Mexico sturgeon *Acipenser oxyrinchus desotoi* (“Gulf sturgeon”) is an anadromous species historically found throughout much of the northern Gulf of Mexico. Gulf sturgeon primarily use freshwater habitats in coastal rivers during much of the year, and return to the Gulf of Mexico during late fall and winter (Huff 1975; Wooley and Crateau 1985; Fox et al. 2000). Gulf sturgeon populations are thought to have declined throughout their range from historical levels, a possible result of overfishing and habitat loss and alteration (Clugston et al. 1995; Zehfuss et al. 1999). As such, Gulf sturgeon are considered “Threatened” under the U.S. Endangered Species Act (ESA, [United States Fish and Wildlife Service 1995]).

Gulf sturgeon experienced a brief, but intense period of commercial fishing during the late nineteenth and early twentieth century (Fig. 1). While these fisheries were relatively short lived, the pattern of exploitation by the fishers clearly demonstrates their effectiveness. Directed fishing for this species has been banned in most states since the mid 1980’s and the species has been listed under the ESA since 1991 providing additional protective status, yet the population viability remains uncertain (United States Fish and Wildlife Service [USFWS] 1995). Gulf sturgeon have evolved a life-history strategy of relatively long-life (20-40+years), late sexual maturity, and specialized spawning and rearing habitats. While these life history strategies have been successful for millions of years, a combination of intensive fishing and habitat modification has possibly led to large population declines.

Estimating abundance of Gulf sturgeon populations has been a primary motivation for many previous studies on this species (Wooley and Crateau 1985, Sulak and Clugston 1999). Closed population estimates are commonly conducted by USFWS, USGS, and ACOE personnel to estimate the abundance of adult Gulf sturgeon in the Pearl River, Mississippi and Apalachicola River, Florida generally during the fall emigration from coastal rivers and also within summer holding areas (Morrow et al. 1998; Zehfuss et al. 1999). Open population estimates have been made for populations in the Suwannee River (Chapman et al. 1997) and open population models were used to also examine population growth rate (~3% annually) in the Suwannee population (Pine et al. 2001). Zehfuss (2000) provides guidance on sampling programs for Gulf

sturgeon to reliably estimate abundance given observed movement patterns and low capture probabilities (generally <10%). Published estimates for Gulf sturgeon abundance generally range from several hundred individuals in the Apalachicola River (for closed models) (Zehfuss et al. 1999) to 5,000-7,000 individuals in the Suwannee River (for open and closed models) (Chapman et al. 1997, Sulak and Clugston 1999).

The overall objective of this study is to develop population models to estimate current and historical abundance of Gulf sturgeon. We used data sets from the Apalachicola and Suwannee rivers, Florida as these systems were thought to have tagging data available over long time periods (early 1980s to present) and represent systems where population abundance was thought to be low (Apalachicola River) and high (Suwannee River). This contrast in abundance would allow for comparison of population model performance with data from populations of different sizes. We estimate population size, age-1 recruitment, and natural mortality by using an age-structured mark-recapture model (ASMR, Coggins et al. 2006a). We reconstruct the historical population size of Gulf sturgeon in Florida waters (where commercial fishing records are available) through retrospective population modeling based on scientific sampling over the last 20 years coupled with historical landings information from early twentieth century. By estimating the current, and reconstructing the historical population size of this species, we attempt to place the current abundance of this species in Florida in a comparative context to assess relative population status from a conservation perspective.

METHODS

Task 1: Life-history Information

Gulf sturgeon life history information was extracted from existing data sets maintained by United States Geologic Survey (USGS), USFWS, Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC), and National Oceanographic Atmospheric Administration – Fisheries (NOAA-Fisheries) and also published and unpublished Gulf sturgeon studies throughout the Gulf of Mexico (Table 1). As part of the Endangered Species Act (ESA) mandated Gulf Sturgeon Recovery Plan (GSRP) (USFWS 1995), information on Gulf sturgeon life history, particularly the location, timing and characteristics of spawning habitats, has been collected for several Gulf sturgeon

populations (Marchant and Shutters 1996, Sulak and Clugston 1998, Fox et al. 2000). Some information such as size-at-maturity was extracted directly from previous studies (Huff 1975) while other information such as maximum age or Gulf sturgeon growth curves were updated based on new estimates derived from research associated with this project.

Tagging data.- Key data used in this report including growth, recruitment, and population abundance information was estimated from capture-recapture sampling for Gulf sturgeon primarily in the Apalachicola (including the Brothers River) and Suwannee rivers. These river systems have been sampled irregularly since the late 1970s or early 1980s primarily by USFWS, USGS, University of Florida, and also Caribbean Conservation Corporation. Tagging data are not continuous for any system, but Suwannee and Apalachicola rivers have received the largest amount of sampling effort. Portions of these data sets have been used previously for similar exercises (e.g., Zehfuss et al. 1999, Pine et al. 2001, Sulak and Randall 2002); however we have updated these data to include Gulf sturgeon capture-recapture records through 2007. The record for each individual Gulf sturgeon included date, location of capture, gear type, total length (TL, mm), fork length (FL, mm), weight (kg), tag type and number, and whether or not the specimen was a recapture. All captured animals were assigned a unique identification number in the data base akin to a social security number. This social security number could then be used to reference all possible tag numbers assigned to each individual animal over the history of the tagging program. All life history information measured with each capture event was also linked back to this unique number.

Characterizing growth. - Describing growth and the size-at-age relationship for Gulf sturgeon is important because this information is used to define age at first tagging in the capture-recapture data and describe other relationships such as weight-at-age, and to calculate sampling vulnerability or mortality. We used length-at-age information from the Apalachicola River (USFWS, unpublished data) combined with Gulf sturgeon tagging data from 1978 to 2007 in the Apalachicola and Suwannee rivers to construct a growth curve using a single likelihood framework (Flowers 2008). The advantages of combining direct aging and tagging data are that the sample size of individuals used for

aging is increased, which likely creates a better representation of the true population growth. Additionally, because many of the data come from direct measures of growth, these errors in measurement are likely additive across all animals instead of systematically biased such as observed with fin-rays.

After estimating standard von Bertalanffy growth parameters, we re-parameterized the growth model into a simplified von Bertalanffy growth curve, recommended by Johnson et al. (2005) for sturgeon species,

$$L_a = L_\infty (1 - e^{-ka}) \quad (1)$$

where L_∞ is the asymptotic length parameter, k is the Brody growth parameter, and L_a is length-at-age. This simplified formulation of the von Bertalanffy assumes that the variable t_0 (age at length zero) is zero and eliminates problems arising from limited size-structure representation in the data set (few very young or old individuals) that could lead to biologically unrealistic estimates of t_0 (Johnson et al. 2005). A single-growth model was used for both sexes in each river as evidence supporting sexually dimorphic growth was inconclusive. Growth curve estimates are included in the life history table (Table 1).

Mortality. - Natural mortality is the average annual rate at which individuals exit the population by death. Estimates of natural mortality are an important parameter for both the mark-recapture abundance estimation (Age-Structured Mark Recapture [ASMR] Coggins et al. 2006a) (Task 2) and the stock reconstruction analysis (SRA) (Task 3). Because capture probabilities for Gulf sturgeon are often low (<10%, Pine et al. 2001) using the ASMR model to simultaneously estimate mortality, abundance, and recruitment can be difficult because of uncertainty in an individual animal's fate each year: was a tagged sturgeon not recaptured because it was dead or simply because the capture probabilities were low? We first estimated natural mortality (M) using life history characteristics such as longevity (Hewitt and Hoenig 2005) or individual metabolic demand (von Bertalanffy k parameter, Jensen 1996). Jensen (1996) proposed a range of relationships between the von Bertalanffy k parameter and M where M is generally equal to about 1.5 - 1.6 the value of k . We found additional evidence for using a 1:1 relationship between M and k ($M = k$) through examining a correlation between estimates of these two parameters published in Fishbase (www.fishbase.org).

Estimates for other sturgeon species developed from tagging and also life history estimates generally estimate annual natural mortality to be 5-10%. As part of this project and Flowers (2008) we have examined a wide range of natural mortality estimates from various life history and direct estimation approaches. The best estimates for Gulf sturgeon natural mortality based on our review of available information range from about 8 to 13% annually. For the ASMR model we estimated M from the data using a lognormal prior value of $M = 0.08$ and standard deviation on this estimate of 0.2.

Task 2: Age-structured Mark-recapture Model

We used ASMR (Coggins et al. 2006b) to estimate abundance and recruitment in the Apalachicola and Suwannee river systems, the two largest river systems on the Florida Gulf coast and the two with the longest-term capture-recapture data available. The ASMR model is basically a traditional Jolly-Seber type open population model combined with a common fisheries virtual population model. This combined approach has worked well in estimating abundance and recruitment patterns for other long-term mark-recapture programs (Coggins et al. 2006b).

The ASMR approach offers an improvement over traditional Jolly-Seber models because the ASMR model estimates recruitment by birth year and not recruitment to the tagged animal pool as in traditional Jolly-Seber models (Coggins et al. 2006a). The ASMR approach is developed by first predicting the number of marked ($\hat{M}_{a,t}$) and unmarked ($\hat{U}_{a,t}$) fish at risk of being caught over each time ($t = 1, \dots, T$) and age ($a = 1, \dots, A$) category. The number of fish caught over time is conditional on the numbers of marked animals in the population and an age specific survival rate where the unmarked individuals are initialized in the terminal year and propagated backwards through time. This is analogous to Virtual Population Analysis (e.g., Figure 1 in Gavaris and Ianelli 2002). The predicted numbers of animals at risk of capture and recapture in each age and year are then estimated as

$$\hat{U}_{a+1,t+1} = \hat{S}_a(\hat{U}_{a,t} - m_{a,t}) \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{M}_{a+1,t+1} = \hat{S}_a(\hat{M}_{a,t} - m_{a,t}) \quad (3)$$

and compared to the observed recaptures for a given year. Note that \hat{S}_a is the average annual survival rate of fish age- a and $m_{a,t}$ is the number of age- a fish marked in year t . The general likelihood function with age and time specific capture probabilities is then maximized where \hat{p}_t is the conditional maximum likelihood estimate of annual capture probability, which is calculated as

$$\hat{p}_t = \frac{\sum_{a=1}^A (m_{a,t} + r_{a,t})}{\sum_{a=1}^A \hat{v}_{a,t} (\hat{U}_{a,t} + \hat{M}_{a,t})} \quad (4)$$

for these observed recaptures. Equation (4) is then maximized to calculate vulnerability ($\hat{v}_{a,t}$), capture probability, and terminal abundance, where abundance of unmarked fish in the terminal year is calculated as

$$\hat{U}_{a,T} = \frac{m_{a,T}}{\hat{p}_{a,T}} \quad (5)$$

leaving the parameters $\hat{v}_{a,t}$, \hat{M}_{adult} , \hat{p}_T to be estimated. Parameter estimation proceeds by minimizing the negative log-likelihood (either a Poisson model or a negative binomial model, see Appendix 1) by varying $\hat{v}_{a,t}$, \hat{M}_{adult} , \hat{p}_T . We assume that the annual natural survival rate is age-specific and time-invariant: age-specific survival is assumed to increase with age as suggested by Lorenzen (2000). Parameter estimation was carried out using ADModel Builder software (<http://admb-project.org>) and posterior distributions were constructed by numerically integrating the joint posterior distribution using the supplied Markov Chain Monte Carlo algorithm within ADModel Builder. Additional details are provided in Appendix 1.

Input parameters for the ASMR model include estimates of L_{inf} and k from the von Bertalanffy growth models and also matrices of captures and recaptures in each year from the tagging program. We assessed two formulations of ASMR (ASMR 1 and ASMR 2) that increase in levels of complexity related to how time and age-specific capture probabilities are calculated in equation 4. ASMR 1 estimates a single capture probability term for all ages and years and ASMR 2 basically allows for time dependent

capture probabilities fixed across age. Full details of the ASMR approach are described in Coggins et al. (2006a).

Two alternative error distributions were explored to assess uncertainty in parameter estimates. First we assumed that the discrete data arise from a Poisson process, and second we assume that the observations arise from a negative binomial process. The Poisson model is more restrictive than the negative binomial model and assumes that the sample variance equals the sample mean. The negative binomial allows the sample variance to exceed the sample mean. The negative binomial model includes an additional estimated parameter (τ) that describes the amount of over-dispersion in the data. Note that when the dispersion parameter approaches infinity, the negative binomial approaches the Poisson model.

Model development. - The ASMR model for the Apalachicola River was initialized with L_{inf} values of 2,177 and 2,344 for the Suwannee River based on von Bertalanffy growth mode fits from a generalized likelihood model that combines growth estimates from hard part estimates with growth information from tag recaptures (Flowers 2008). A maximum age of 50 was assumed based on our reconstructed maximum age from tag recoveries. A lognormally distributed prior for M of 0.08 with a standard deviation of 0.2 was used for all ASMR formulations. A Lorenzen type mortality function was used to adjust M estimates by fish length: higher M for smaller younger fish, lower M for the largest, oldest fish (Coggins et al. 2006a).

Estimates of abundance, capture probability and recruitment were made from 1977 to 2007 for the Apalachicola River and 1984 to 2007 for the Suwannee River. Years in which sampling did not occur were not included in the likelihood formulation to reduce negative bias in capture probability due to zero sampling effort. Tag-loss rates were assumed to be 5% for all ages over all years.

Task 3: Stock Reduction Analysis

We developed an age-structured stock reduction analysis (SRA) model which is basically a standard population dynamics model using age-structured representations of growth, survival, and recruitment that simulates forward from a historical reference point prior to the beginning of fishery exploitation. Details of the SRA approach used are

available in Walters et al. (2006) and the general framework is reproduced here. Numbers of Gulf sturgeon were assumed to change over age a and years t following

$$N_{(a+1,t+1)} = (N_{a,t} S (1 - v_{a,t} U_t)) \quad (6)$$

$$a = 1 \dots 50, t = 1890 \dots 2008$$

where $S = e^{-M}$ is the natural survival rate and $v_{a,t}$ is the vulnerability of fish age a to fishing in year t and U_t is an estimate of the exploitation rate of fully vulnerable fish ($v_a = 1$) in year t . The vulnerability schedule was assumed to generally follow a normal distribution based on examination of catches from the commercial landings and scientific sampling. The age at 50% vulnerability was assumed to be age-5. The exploitation rate in each year U_t can be calculated from the historical total catches C_t as

$$U_t = \frac{C_t}{\sum_a N_{a,t} v_{a,t} w_a} \quad (7)$$

where w_a is the average weight of a fish age a . We assumed a Beverton-Holt stock-recruitment relationship using the compensation form of the equation (Walters and Martell 2004)

$$N_{1,t+1} = \frac{K \left(\frac{R_o}{E_o} \right) E_t}{1 + \frac{K-1}{E_o} E_t} \quad (8)$$

where R_o is a parameter to be estimated that represents the average unfished age-1 recruitment, E_o is average annual egg production for an unfished population with recruitment R_o , and K is the Goodyear recruitment compensation ratio. The recruitment compensation ratio describes the steepness of the stock-recruitment curve at low stock size as the ratio of juvenile survival rate at low stock size to juvenile survival rate in the unfished population. Higher K values imply populations that have higher compensatory juvenile survival at low population sizes relative to unexploited population sizes. This implies that populations with high K values are more resilient to exploitation than populations with low K values because they have a stronger compensatory response (Walters and Martell 2004). We estimated K following the approach in Martell et al. (2008) which used the management parameters of maximum sustained yield (MSY) and the exploitation rate needed to achieve this yield (F_{MSY} ; Pine et al. 2008). This approach provides probability density estimates for a range of K parameter values.

From the population created by this model we removed historical catches reported each year, debit each age class by natural mortality, and added recruits in each year to develop a cumulative prediction of the current (2008) stock status. For years with missing landings records we either averaged the preceding and following year landings (for gaps of 2-4 years) or for longer time periods we assumed an exponential decay between years of known landings. This backfilling of catches was checked by comparing predicted landings to reports by US Bureau of Fisheries agents who characterized the landings in these years by describing ranges of values, but no year-specific reports were available (Flowers 2008). We adjusted recruitment estimates in the simulations to produce population abundance estimates that were near current abundance estimates. We used Monte-Carlo simulations to generate probability distributions for past stock sizes given different hypotheses of mean natural recruitment levels and variation in standard stock-recruitment relationships. For each Monte-Carlo simulation in which recruitment estimates provided in the model were too low to have sustained the historical catches, the SRA model predicts that the population should have gone extinct. When estimated recruitment rates are too high, the SRA model predicts that the historical fishing impact and, the current population size are too large. Basically, the SRA model is fit to historical landings data by adjusting recruitment parameters to create a history of the population that includes both the historical fishing impacts (driven by the landings) and recruitment patterns that yield population estimates near those we estimate from the capture-recapture data. Sensitivity to different combinations of R_0 and K were examined by fitting a large range of K values to examine how this affected R_0 estimates.

RESULTS

Assessing Plots of Cumulative Marks and Recaptures

Apalachicola River. -Since 1977, at least 1,132 Gulf sturgeon have been tagged in the Apalachicola River and there were 404 recapture events (Fig. 2a). A plot of cumulative captures (new tags) and recaptures (of previously tagged animals) in each year (Fig. 2a) shows a stair-step pattern in captures. Bubble plots of the log+1 of the number of tags released and recaptured in the Apalachicola River show changes in number of fish

marked and recaptured each year related to shifts in sampling program design (Fig. 3a, b).

Suwannee River. - Since 1982, 6,615 Gulf sturgeon have been tagged in the Suwannee River and there have been 2,515 recapture events (Fig. 2b). No clear patterns in the cumulative tags and recaptures are evident in the Suwannee River. In general, the highest tagging efforts were in the early 1990s with much lower tagging efforts since this time. A period of limited tagging and recapture effort in the early 2000s is evident and recent increases in tagging effort show an increase in numbers of newly tagged animals (Fig. 3c, d), but a low rate of recaptures. Recapture rates are generally low and stable throughout the time series (Figs. 2b and 3c, d).

Estimates of Gulf sturgeon Abundance, Mortality, Recruitment, and Capture Probability

Apalachicola River.- In the Apalachicola River, the ASMR model formulations 1 and 2 with the Poisson and negative binomial error structures generally estimate <400 age 2+ sturgeon in the early 1980s and increasing to between 500-100 age 2+ sturgeon by 2005 (Fig. 4). Recent abundance estimates were highly variable depending on the model error structure assumed. ASMR 1 results for recent years show declines in population abundance while ASMR 2 results do not show this decline (Fig. 4). Residual plots for marks and recaptures for ASMR model 1 show poor model fit for recent sampling years (Fig. 5). Mortality estimates (M) for the Apalachicola River ranged from about 5 to 7% depending on the model formulation and error term assumed (Fig. 6, Appendix 1 Table 6).

Recruitment patterns show similar trends as the abundance estimates with generally low recruitment through much of the 1980s and gradual recruitment increases in the 1990s and early 2000s (Fig. 7). ASMR 1 estimates low and highly variable recruitment throughout the time series while ASMR 2 suggests an increasing trend in recruitment with recruitment estimated to have doubled in the since about 2000 over the earlier years in the time series.

Capture probability estimates were low and variable with capture probability generally 10-15% in years when sampling takes place (Fig. 8). These variations in

capture probability are also apparent in plots of the logarithm of marks and recaptures (Fig. 3a, b) which demonstrate limited sampling in some years. In years where sampling effort was high (i.e., mid-1980s), relatively large cohorts of tagged fish are marked and these tag fish cohorts persist for long-time periods in the data (Fig. 3).

Suwannee River.- For the Suwannee River, population abundance estimates for age 2+ Gulf sturgeon differ between the two ASMR formulations evaluated (Fig. 9). ASMR 1 (for both error formulations) shows increases in Gulf sturgeon abundance from the early 1980s to a peak of around 5,000 individuals around 1990, with a steady decline from that point until present (Fig. 9a, b). ASMR 2 estimates a different pattern with increases in abundance from around 2,000 individuals in the mid-1980's with peaks in abundance in the mid-1990s of around 5,000 individuals (Fig. 9c, d). ASMR 2 with a Poisson error structure estimates a steady decline in age 2+ Gulf sturgeon from this point to around 3,000 individuals in 2005, while ASMR 2 with a negative binomial error structure predicts relatively stable, but highly uncertain, abundance estimates from the mid-1990s until 2005. Residual patterns of marks and recaptures from the ASMR models (Figure 10) show a general pattern of slightly higher predicted captures and recaptures than what was observed. Mortality estimates for the Suwannee River ranged from about 10 to 20% depending on the error term used (Fig. 11).

Recruitment patterns in the Suwannee River show a pattern of increasing recruitment from the late 1970s and early 1980s with peaks occurring in the early and mid 1990s. Recruitment patterns since the mid-1990s to present are estimated to be highly variable with an overall declining trend in both ASMR 1 and 2 for both error term formulations (Fig. 12).

Suwannee River age 2+ Gulf sturgeon capture probabilities increased from the mid-1980s to a peak in the early 1990s with capture probabilities approaching 20% in the 1990s when sampling efforts were higher while in recent years capture probabilities have been much lower (Fig. 13). This is apparent in the plots of the logarithm of new marks and recaptures in each year (Fig. 3) where a wide distribution of fish of different ages were tagged in the 1990s and these cohorts persisted in subsequent years of sampling even in years with low sampling effort such as the early 2000s.

Stock Reduction Analysis

Stock reduction analysis results suggest that Gulf sturgeon population biomass in Florida prior to the beginning of fishing in the late 1800s was likely a minimum of 600,000-700,000 kg. Current Gulf sturgeon population biomass estimates from the SRA indicate that the current population is approximately 20-30% of the historic population biomass levels. Estimated K for Gulf sturgeon was 4, similar to the estimated value ($K=5$) for white sturgeon (Walters et al. 2006). This value is relatively low across species (Goodwin et al. 2006), but would be expected given sturgeon life history characteristics of long life and late sexual maturation (Pine et al. 2001).

DISCUSSION

Our results for Gulf sturgeon in the Suwannee and Apalachicola rivers suggest that population biomass for this species was severely reduced by about 90% during a short, but intense, period of commercial harvest. After large-scale fishing was abandoned, a small (exploitation less than 5% annually), but sustainable, fishery persisted until closed via regulation in the early 1980s. Gulf sturgeon populations in the rivers that likely supported the largest fisheries (Apalachicola and Suwannee rivers) have demonstrated stable, to slightly increasing populations during the last 20 years. However, a combination of life-history characteristics (skip spawning, where individuals do not return to spawn each year), behavior (gear avoidance), and variations in sampling programs (effort and location) all contribute to uncertainty in current population estimates, which could lead to divergent management policies related to this listed species.

Key inferences on the status of this species and the capabilities of the current monitoring programs can be made by simply examining plots of the data. The stair-step pattern evident in the plots of cumulative captures and recaptures is likely reflective of increases in effort and/or resumption of directed sampling for capturing adult fish following several years of low sampling efforts (Figs. 2 and 3). This increase in cumulative captures (open circles of Fig. 2) occurs when the number of unmarked animals has increased due to births, skip spawning fish simply being present in the system and available for capture, or shifts in area sampled.

For example, the large increase in the number of animals tagged since 2000 in the Apalachicola River could be due to a shift in the sampling away from long-term sample sites below Jim Woodruff Dam to other summer holding areas in the Brothers River. Pine et al. (2006) reported on results of adult sturgeon movement studies between different summer holding areas in the Apalachicola River basin and how these movement patterns, and shifts in the sampling program, can create uncertainty in interpreting tagging data. Cumulative captures and recaptures shown in Fig. 2a for the Apalachicola River may demonstrate this. While the number of tagged individuals has basically tripled from about 400 individuals in the late 1990s to more than 1,200 individuals in recent years, the number of recaptures during this same time period has not quite doubled. Additionally, the rate of recaptures (basically the slope of the recapture line in Fig. 2a) has remained relatively flat during the 1990s, a time period when much of the sampling occurred below Jim Woodruff Dam. Since the late 1990s the recapture rate has increased, but while the number of marks has increased by 2–3 times (the open circles in Fig 2a), the number of recaptures has only increased by about 50%. There are two simple explanations for this observation.

First, given the low recapture rate of Gulf sturgeon (for reasons discussed in Pine et al. 2006 such as gear avoidance and skip spawning) and the shift in the sampling program to the Brothers River (and possible shift in adult sturgeon habitat utilization to this location) it will take several years of effort to increase the recaptures in this location due to site fidelity to summer holding areas. Low recapture rates possibly could be addressed through intensive reanalysis of all available telemetry data linked to age/size structured estimation of capture probabilities in ASMR. This shift in the sampling location was in part motivated by large declines in catch-rates of adult Gulf sturgeon at the Jim Woodruff Dam location (Pine et al. 2006) and the issue of whether Gulf sturgeon have left this site or a change in the selectivity pattern of the gears should be addressed (Pine et al. 2006).

A second explanation could be either an increase in tag loss rates either through shedding or a systematic failure in the Passive Integrated Transponder (PIT) tag scanners to detect and decode previously tagged fish. This is possibly of greater concern because uncertainty in tag retention or some sort of systematic problem with

decreases in PIT tag detection, possibly suggesting a need for re-evaluation of the current tagging program. This could possibly be assessed by re-configuring the Apalachicola River tagging data base to look for changes in capture probability through time by tag type. Fish monitoring programs in the Colorado River basin have noted declines in detection rate of PIT tags >10 years old due either to changes in the ability of PIT tag scanners to detect these tags, or some sort of failure in the tag themselves (L. Coggins, USGS-GCMRC, Flagstaff, Arizona, personal communication). This has led this group to re-tag all recaptured fish tagged with have an “old” 400-khz PIT tags with new 134.2-khz PIT tags to reduce the chance of losing the capture history of these animals.

Our estimated mortality rates from the tagging data of 5-7% annually in the Apalachicola River and 10-20% in the Suwannee River differ from the values estimated from life history correlates of about 8-13%. Pine et al. (2001) using tagging data from 1986-1995 estimated mortality rates for adult Gulf sturgeon in the Suwannee River of about 16%. Morrow et al. (1998) estimated mortality rate of Gulf sturgeon in the Pearl River, MS of about 34% and recommended that mortality rates of 15-22% would most likely be required for the population to recovery. Our mortality estimate for Gulf sturgeon in the Suwannee River is higher than would be expected based on life history invariants. These mortality estimates are likely biased by limited sampling efforts in the early 2000s (Figs. 3 and 13) leading to zero or very low capture probabilities until 2006, when sampling intensity (and capture probability) greatly increased. Because of these changes in sampling effort, it is simply difficult to separate in the model whether older Gulf sturgeon were not captured because of low capture probability or if these fish had died. Examining the plots of the logarithms of marks and recaptures (Fig. 3) demonstrates the persistence of tagged cohorts in the population. For example, Gulf sturgeon tagged in the Suwannee River in 1993 have been consistently recaptured in each subsequent year of sampling demonstrating long persistence of fish from multiple age-classes.

Our estimates of age-1 recruitment from the ASMR model for the Apalachicola River show generally low recruitment through much of the 1980's and gradual recruitment increases in the 1990s and early 2000s (Fig. 4). Age-1 recruitment

estimates for the Suwannee River show highest recruitment estimates in the 1980s and 1990s with declining estimates in the 2000s (Fig. 12). Caution should be taken in interpreting the relative recruitment of any particular year in comparison to years immediately preceding or following as inaccuracies in the assignment of age-at-first capture (which would determine the brood year) could lead to a smearing in age-assignments by 1-2 years. This smearing would thus making it difficult to identify year-to-year responses in recruitment to management actions or spawning conditions (Coggins et al. 2006b) so assessing recruitment estimates for an individual year are not recommended.

Each ASMR formulation represents different assumptions about the structure of the data, which are driven by the sampling programs and the biology of the species. The primary difference between ASMR 1 and ASMR 2 is the number of estimated parameters; ASMR 1 has 4 or 5 unknowns for the Poisson and negative binomial likelihoods respectively, whereas ASMR 2 has 30 and 31 for the Poisson and negative binomial models (see Appendix 1). ASMR 2 estimates the terminal numbers at age, whereas ASMR 1 estimates the terminal capture probability (\hat{p}_T) and reconstructs the terminal numbers based on the mark information in the last year. As the models progress from 1 to 2 greater resolution in the data is needed to estimate the additional parameters contained in each ASMR formulae. For example, to be able to reliably estimate age and time-dependent capture probabilities estimates, capture probabilities must be relative high for each age and year or sampling to separate whether an animal was present and not caught or not present in the system.

We compared ASMR estimates of population size to other published and unpublished population size estimates in the Apalachicola River (Fig. 14). In general, previous abundance estimates were made for sub-adult or adult fish captured with gill nets in summer holding areas (Pine et al. 2006). Flowers (2008) identified asymptotic vulnerability schedules for Gulf sturgeon in gill nets and Pine et al. (2001) suggest that Gulf sturgeon do not become fully vulnerable to gill nets until age-6. Because the ASMR results are age-structured and include a vulnerability schedule for recaptures of marked animals and a VPA estimate of the unmarked individuals, ASMR estimates include the abundance of younger fish (which are more abundant). For comparison, we

have included a plot of the ASMR 2 results for age 2+ Gulf sturgeon from the Apalachicola River along with the closed population estimates from previous (Zehfuss 1999; Pine et al. 2006) studies for the same population. This comparison shows that in general ASMR estimates are higher than closed population estimates but the two approaches show similar increasing trends in abundance (Fig. 14). These differences are most likely a function of differences in the data and model structure used in the two approaches because the ASMR results include the abundance of smaller, younger fish than the closed population estimates. Regardless of the differences in abundance estimates, both models, with very different assumptions and structure, show increasing trends in Apalachicola River Gulf sturgeon populations.

A commonly used fisheries benchmark to assess population status is to estimate the spawning potential ratio (SPR) as annual egg production under harvest divided by annual egg production of an unexploited stock (Goodyear 1980, Walters and Martell 2004). Exploited fisheries are often managed to minimize the chance of recruitment overfishing (i.e., harvest exceeding replacement rate) by setting SPR target values to exceed 0.4, that is, the current (exploited) population should have at least 40% the reproductive capacity of the unexploited stock. Using the SRA model and information from Flowers (2008), the current SPR ranges for Gulf sturgeon are likely 0.3 to 0.5 suggesting that Gulf sturgeon recruitment rates are at or above a common management benchmark. This result is supported by observations in the data and from the ASMR estimates of generally increasing recruitment patterns and a rebuilding in the age-structure of the Gulf sturgeon population in Apalachicola Rivers (but uncertain in the Suwannee River) evident in the bubble plots of marks and recaptures by age (Fig. 3). Given the low K values we estimated for Gulf sturgeon (about 4) and the long-lived, late maturing aspects of Gulf sturgeon life history, management targets for SPR should likely be higher than 0.4. If populations increase, this target SPR level will likely be met. Our SRA results demonstrate that Gulf sturgeon populations can likely only support very low annual harvest with F_{MSY} values of 0.04-0.08 annually. This is much lower than SRA estimated patterns in landings where annual exploitation during the peak of the fisheries was approximately 0.3 (Fig. 15).

An important component of Gulf sturgeon recovery is that the abundance of Gulf sturgeon may be more rapidly recovering than the age structure and population biomass. The rapid decline in Gulf sturgeon landings is likely reflective of quick erosion of the population age structure where the majority of the early landings were made up of large, older fish. Given Gulf sturgeon life-history characteristics, such as long life, slow growth, and high age at maturity, it is quite likely that the recovery of the population age-structure (and biomass) will take many more years than the recovery of the abundance. Slow population recovery time in highly exploited fisheries caused the lag in population growth rate related to rebuilding the population age-structure and spawning capacity (Walters et al. 2008). Gulf sturgeon population recovery rate should increase as population age structure continues to mature (Flowers 2008).

MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study our estimated mortality rates from the tagging data collected as part of the monitoring program are higher in the Suwannee River than those calculated for the Apalachicola River or than what would be expected based on life history information. This does not suggest that any of the estimates (from ASMR or based on life-history) are correct. However, when these different mortality rates are included as part of ASMR model to assess recent trends in abundance the resulting estimates of population trajectory range can be either increasing or decreasing – results which would likely necessitate different responses from resource managers. For example, if M is not estimated as part of ASMR, and life history based estimates of M are assumed, then the ASMR model estimates larger populations and positive population growth in both the Apalachicola and Suwannee rivers since the 1980s – a key expectation under the Gulf Sturgeon Recovery Plan (USFWS 1995). However, when mortality is estimated as part of the ASMR model, both rivers are estimated to have smaller populations and possibly population declines in abundance in recent years. This result, particularly the recent population declines, is likely of concern to resource managers charged with developing recovery policies for this species.

It is easy to discount this result as simply a function of sparse data and poor model fits and assume that the problem will fix itself with a few more years of data.

However, can this risk be afforded given the costs (change in listing status, and associated regulatory policy changes) of being wrong? What if Gulf sturgeon populations are on a downward trajectory increasing their risk of jeopardy? This is an example of where the high costs for information needed to accurately assess the status of a stock (in this case, well designed and funded long-term monitoring programs) must be measured against the costs of incorrect policy choices such as species jeopardy or societal costs such as lost revenues or employment opportunities (Walters and Maguire 1996, Walters and Martell 2004) particularly in the Apalachicola River basin which is at the center of one of the longest-running water disputes in the eastern United States (Flowers et al. 2009).

Key management recommendations from this study include:

- (1) Developing temporal and spatial consistency in Gulf sturgeon monitoring programs. Previous work funded by the USFWS on the Apalachicola River (Zehfuss 2000) found that the power to detect a decline in Gulf sturgeon populations increased with larger sturgeon population sizes, larger changes in population abundance, a higher probability of capturing or recapturing individual fish, and a long time period of sampling. Through a simulation model based on capture probabilities and population size for the Apalachicola River Gulf sturgeon population, Zehfuss (2000) found that to detect a population decline of at least 5-10% per year a sampling program of at least seven consecutive years would have to be conducted.
- (2) Evaluate current tagging programs for problems associated with systematic failures in PIT tag detections. PIT tag and tag reader performance is known to vary widely (Fuller et al. 2008). Incomplete detection of previously tagged animals (a type of tag shedding) can lead to biases in population abundance estimates and inflation of mortality estimates. Standardization of PIT tags and readers as part of a revised monitoring program is recommended.
- (3) Develop a standardized, centralized database and sampling coordination office for archiving historical data collection efforts, coordinating tagging efforts and equipment, standardizing data collected by field personnel, and developing electronic tag reconstruction algorithms.

- (4) Conduct stock assessments on regular intervals (likely 3-5 years) to assess patterns in mortality rates, population trend, and survival.

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Table 1. Parameter definitions and life history values for Gulf sturgeon populations in the Apalachicola and Suwannee rivers, Florida.

Parameter	Description	Value	Source
F_{msy}	Fishing mortality at maximum sustained yield	0.05-0.08	Pine et al. 2008
k	Brody growth parameter	0.13	Flowers 2008
L_{∞}	Von Bertalanffy asymptotic length parameter	2177 mm Apalachicola, 2344 mm Suwannee River	Flowers 2008
M	Annual natural mortality, overall	8-13%	Flowers 2008
N	Population size in a given year	Estimated	This report
N_0	Initial pre-exploitation population size	~30,000	Pine et al. 2008
N_{1985}	Population size at end of harvest	282 (181-645)	Wooley and Crateau 1985
$reck$	Goodyear recruitment compensation parameter	4	USFWS and USGS-FISC tagging data 1978-2006, Martell et al. 2008
Sk	Factor to adjust skip spawning effects	1-5 year intervals	Sulak and Clugston 1999, Pine et al. 2001
W_{mat}	Weight at maturity	10.8 kg	Huff 1975, Flowers 2008
Ma_i	First age at maturity	6	Huff 1975
V	Vulnerability-at-age	variable-at-age	Flowers 2008

Fig. 1. Reported annual commercial fishery landings for Gulf sturgeon (y-axis, kg) landings for Florida waters.

Fig. 2. Cumulative numbers of Gulf sturgeon (Y-axis) marked and recaptured in the Apalachicola River (panel a) and the Suwannee River (panel b) through time (Year, X-axis).

Figure 3: Number of marks released and recaptured in the Apalachicola River (panels a and b, respectively) and in the Suwannee River (panels c and d). The diameter of each circle is proportional to the log of the number of tags released + 1, and the total number of tags released and recaptured each year is at the top of the column.

Figure 4: Estimates of age 2+ numbers for the Apalachicola River using ASMR1 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels a and b, respectively), and ASMR2 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels c and d).

Figure 5: Residual patterns for new marks and recaptured marks in ASMR1 (panels a and b, respectively) and ASMR2 in panels c and d in the Apalachicola River assuming a negative binomial distribution for the loglikelihood. The diameter of each circle is directly proportional to the difference between the observed and predicted number of marks; open and closed circles represent positive and negative residuals, respectively.

Figure 6: Marginal posterior density and the assumed prior density for the instantaneous natural mortality rate in ASMR1 and ASMR1 using both the Poisson likelihood (a) and negative binomial likelihood (b). Results based on mark data for sturgeon in the Apalachicola River.

Figure 7: Estimates of age-1 recruits for the Apalachicola River using ASMR1 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels a and b, respectively), and ASMR2 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels c and d). Solid lines represent median estimates and dashed lines represent 95% credible intervals.

Figure 8: Estimates of capture probabilities for the Apalachicola River using ASMR1 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels a and b, respectively), and ASMR2 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels c and d). Solid lines represent median estimates and dashed lines represent 95% credible intervals.

Figure 9: Estimates of age 2+ numbers for the Suwannee River using ASMR1 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels a and b, respectively), and ASMR2 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels c and d). Solid lines represent median estimates and dashed lines represent 95% credible intervals.

Figure 10: Residual patterns for new marks and recaptured marks in ASMR1 (panels a and b, respectively) and ASMR2 in panels c and d in the Suwannee River assuming a negative binomial distribution for the loglikelihood. The diameter of each circle is directly proportional to the difference between the observed and predicted number of marks; open and closed circles represent positive and negative residuals, respectively.

Figure 11: Marginal posterior density and the assumed prior density for the instantaneous natural mortality rate in ASMR1 and ASMR1 using both the Poisson likelihood (a) and negative binomial likelihood (b). Results based on mark data for sturgeon in the Suwannee River.

Figure 12: Estimates of age-1 recruits for the Suwannee River using ASMR1 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels a and b, respectively), and ASMR2 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels c and d). Solid lines represent median estimates and dashed lines represent 95% credible intervals.

Figure 13: Estimates of capture probabilities for the Suwannee River using ASMR1 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels a and b, respectively), and ASMR2 with the negative binomial and Poisson likelihoods (panels c and d). Solid lines represent median estimates and dashed lines represent 95% credible intervals.

Figure 14: Estimates of 2+ abundance for the Apalachicola River using ASMR2 and a negative binomial likelihood with 95% credible intervals (solid and dashed lines), and closed population estimates (squares) from USFWS with confidence intervals (open triangles).

Fig. 15. Estimated annual exploitation (u) by year from the stock reduction analysis (SRA) for Gulf sturgeon from Florida waters based on reported commercial fisheries landings from various state and federal fisheries management reports (see text).

APPENDIX

We use an age-structured mark-recapture model (ASMR) to jointly estimate natural mortality, annual capture probabilities, and age-specific vulnerabilities using three alternative model formulations with two alternative assumptions about the error distributions in the data. The simplest version of ASMR is described in Appendix Table 1, additional details and assumptions about ASMR are detailed in Coggins et al. (2006a). Annual observations (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.1) consist of a number of marks released each year of a given age ($m_{t,a}$) and the number of marked fish at age recaptured ($r_{t,a}$) at least one year from the initial marking. The estimated parameter vector (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.2) consists of the instantaneous natural mortality rate (M), the capture probability in the terminal year for fish that are fully vulnerable to the sampling gear, and parameters for an age-specific selectivity curve for the sampling gear. We assume that the annual natural survival rate is age-specific and time invariant; age-specific survival is assumed to increase with age (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.3) following Lorenzen (2000). We further assume that all fish die after the age $A = 50$. Age-specific vulnerability to the sampling gear is assumed to follow a logistic curve (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.4) with the parameters \hat{a} and $\hat{\sigma}$ describing the age at 50% vulnerability and the standard deviation, respectively.

The age-structured accounting system in ASMR keeps track of both the number of marked ($M_{t,a}$) and unmarked ($U_{t,a}$) fish in the population, where the unmarked individuals are initialized in the terminal year (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.5) and propagated backwards through time (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.7). This is analogous to Virtual Population Analysis (e.g., Figure 1. in Gavaris and Ianelli [2002]). The number of marked individuals is initialized in the first year (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.6) and the number of marked fish at

large is updated following equation 8 (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.8). The year and age-specific capture probability is given by equation 9 (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.9) and the predicted number of new marks released and recaptured marks is given by equation 10 (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.10) and 11 (Appendix Table 1, Equation 1.11).

The standardized residuals for the Poisson model are given by equations 1 and 2 in Appendix Table 2 (Appendix Table 2, Equation 2.1 and 2.2) for the number of marks at large and recaptures. The joint log-likelihood for the new marks and recaptures is given by equation 3 (Appendix Table 2, Equation 2.3). The standardized residuals for the negative binomial model are given by equations found in Appendix Table 3, Equation 3.1 and 3.2). Note that as the dispersion parameter $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, then the negative binomial model approaches the Poisson model. The joint log-likelihood function for the negative binomial model is given by equation 3 in Appendix Table 3 with the additional constraint that $\tau > 0$.

In addition to the ASMR model 1 specified in Appendix Table 1, we also explored a more complex model that included additional parameters for estimating the terminal numbers in year T , instead of a single terminal capture probability (P_T). In this case, the estimated parameter vector, defined by equation 2 in Appendix Table 4 directly estimates the number of individuals (in log space $X_{T,a}$) from age-1 to a user specified terminal age- A_t . The remaining terminal numbers older than age A_T are initialized assuming a stable age distribution dictated by the age-specific survival rate (Appendix Table 4, Equation 4.6). All other calculations leading up to the predicted number of new marks and predicted recaptures are the same as those specified in Table 1.

Table 1: Age-structured mark-recapture model with logistic selectivity and a terminal capture probability.

Observations	
$m_{t,a}, r_{t,a}$	(T1.1)
Estimated parameters	
$\theta = (M, P_T, \hat{a}, \hat{\gamma})$	(T1.2)
Age-schedule variables	
$s_a = \left(\frac{k(a+1)}{ka} \frac{1}{1} \right)^{-(M-k)}$	(T1.3)
$v_a = [1 + \exp((\hat{a} - a) \hat{\gamma})]^{-1}$	(T1.4)
Initial states	
$U_{t,a} = m_{t,a} (P_T, v_a) \quad t = T$	(T1.5)
$M_{t,a} = 0 \quad t = 1$	(T1.6)
State dynamics	
$U_{t,a} = (U_{t+1,a+1} s_a) + m_{t,a}$	(T1.7)
$M_{t+1,a+1} = s_a (M_{t,a} + m_{t,a})$	(T1.8)
$P_{t,a} = \frac{m_{t,a} + r_{t,a}}{v_a (U_{t,a} + M_{t,a})}$	(T1.9)
Predicted observations	
$\hat{m}_{t,a} = U_{t,a} P_{t,a}$	(T1.10)
$\hat{r}_{t,a} = M_{t,a} P_{t,a}$	(T1.11)

Table 2: Residuals and negative log-likelihoods for poisson model.

Residuals for poisson model

$$\epsilon_{t,a} = \frac{m_{t,a} - \hat{m}_{t,a}}{\sqrt{\hat{m}_{t,a}}} \quad (\text{T2.1})$$

$$\delta_{t,a} = \frac{r_{t,a} - \hat{r}_{t,a}}{\sqrt{\hat{r}_{t,a}}} \quad (\text{T2.2})$$

Poisson log-likelihood

$$\ell(m, r | \theta) = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{a=1}^A [\hat{m}_{t,a} - m_{t,a} \ln(\hat{m}_{t,a})] + \sum_{t=2}^T \sum_{a=2}^A [\hat{r}_{t,a} - r_{t,a} \ln(\hat{r}_{t,a})] \quad (\text{T2.3})$$

Table 3: Residuals and negative log-likelihoods for the negative binomial model.

Residuals for the negative binomial model

$$\epsilon_{t,a} = \frac{m_{t,a} \hat{m}_{t,a}}{\sqrt{\hat{m}_{t,a} + (\hat{m}_{t,a})^2/\tau}} \quad (\text{T3.1})$$

$$\delta_{t,a} = \frac{r_{t,a} \hat{r}_{t,a}}{\sqrt{\hat{r}_{t,a} + (\hat{r}_{t,a})^2/\tau}} \quad (\text{T3.2})$$

Negative binomial log-likelihood

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{r}, \theta, \tau) = & \\ & \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{a=1}^A \ln \Gamma(\tau + m_{t,a}) - \ln \Gamma(\tau) + \tau \ln(\tau/(\tau + \hat{m}_{t,a})) + m_{t,a} \ln(\hat{m}_{t,a} / (\tau + \hat{m}_{t,a})) \\ & \sum_{t=2}^T \sum_{a=2}^A \ln \Gamma(\tau + r_{t,a}) - \ln \Gamma(\tau) + \tau \ln(\tau/(\tau + \hat{r}_{t,a})) + r_{t,a} \ln(\hat{r}_{t,a} / (\tau + \hat{r}_{t,a})) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{T3.3})$$

Table 4: Age-structured mark-recapture model with logistic selectivity and terminal numbers-at-age.

Observations	
$m_{t,a}, r_{t,a}$	(T4.1)
Estimated parameters	
$\theta = (M, \hat{a}, \hat{\gamma}, \quad T, a \quad a=1 \quad a=A_T)$	(T4.2)
Age-schedule variables	
$s_a = \left(\frac{k(a+1)}{ka} \frac{1}{1} \right)^{(M-k)}$	(T4.3)
$v_a = [1 + \exp((\hat{a} - a) \hat{\gamma})]^{-1}$	(T4.4)
Initial states	
$U_{t,a} = \exp(-r_{t,a}) \quad t = T, \quad 2 \leq a \leq A_T$	(T4.5)
$U_{t,a} = U_{t,a-1} s_{a-1} \quad t = T, \quad A_T - a \leq A$	(T4.6)
$M_{t,a} = 0 \quad t = 1$	(T4.7)
State dynamics	
$U_{t,a} = (U_{t+1,a+1} s_a) + m_{t,a}$	(T4.8)
$M_{t+1,a+1} = s_a (M_{t,a} + m_{t,a})$	(T4.9)
$p_{t,a} = \frac{m_{t,a} + r_{t,a}}{v_a (U_{t,a} + M_{t,a})}$	(T4.10)
Predicted observations	
$\hat{m}_{t,a} = U_{t,a} p_{t,a}$	(T4.11)
$\hat{r}_{t,a} = M_{t,a} p_{t,a}$	(T4.12)

Table 5: Number of estimated parameters (N) the negative loglikelihood and estimate of the instantaneous natural mortality rate for each of the age structured mark recapture models (ASMR; P and NB correspond to the Poisson and negative binomial likelihood formulations).

River	Model	No. Pars	nloglikelihood	M
Apalachicola	ASMR 1 P	4	-848.03	0.0722
	ASMR 1 NB	5	-922.76	0.0716
	ASMR 2 P	29	-960.08	0.0498
	ASMR 2 NB	30	-985.78	0.0502
Suwannee	ASMR 1 P	4	-22306.6	0.2090
	ASMR 1 NB	5	-23413.9	0.2105
	ASMR 2 P	29	-22660.8	0.1481
	ASMR 2 NB	30	-23847.2	0.1000

Table 6: Maximum likelihood estimates (MLE) and standard deviation (STD) of parameters for ASMR 1 and 2 using either the Poisson distribution or the Negative binomial distribution as the likelihood function. The negative binomial model has an additional over-dispersion parameter (τ).

Parameter	Apalachicola		Suwannee		Apalachicola		Suwannee	
	MLE	STD	MLE	STD	MLE	STD	MLE	STD
	ASMR 1 Poisson				ASMR 1 Negative Binomial			
M	0.07	0.00	0.21	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.21	0.01
p_T	0.09	0.01	0.35	0.03	0.11	0.02	0.48	0.14
\hat{a}	1.63	0.09	4.26	0.08	1.91	0.17	2.95	0.46
$\hat{\gamma}$	2.38	0.31	0.84	0.02	1.61	0.31	1.63	0.36
τ					4.13	0.63	0.32	0.02
Parameter	Apalachicola		Suwannee		Apalachicola		Suwannee	
	MLE	STD	MLE	STD	MLE	STD	MLE	STD
	ASMR 2 Poisson				ASMR 2 Negative Binomial			
M	0.05	0.00	0.15	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.10	0.01
\hat{a}	1.73	0.11	3.67	0.10	1.83	0.16	2.86	0.23
$\hat{\gamma}$	2.18	0.31	0.79	0.02	1.75	0.32	0.88	0.08
τ					7.54	1.63	2.94	0.23
T ₁	5.78	1.05	5.61	0.59	5.50	1.09	5.92	0.84
T ₂	5.97	0.32	6.18	0.22	5.81	0.41	6.58	0.50
T ₃	5.09	0.28	5.87	0.20	4.95	0.40	6.61	0.45
T ₄	4.69	0.26	4.25	0.35	4.43	0.39	4.74	0.56
T ₅	4.70	0.21	5.16	0.20	4.57	0.31	5.66	0.46
T ₆	5.18	0.18	5.75	0.16	4.78	0.30	6.13	0.40
T ₇	3.58	0.29	5.59	0.15	3.49	0.36	5.91	0.34
T ₈	2.64	0.42	5.26	0.16	2.59	0.48	5.66	0.34
T ₉	3.44	0.31	4.60	0.17	3.24	0.40	5.31	0.34
T ₁₀	4.08	0.21	4.40	0.17	3.74	0.31	5.20	0.32
T ₁₁	3.34	0.27	4.37	0.16	3.14	0.36	5.43	0.31
T ₁₂	2.49	0.40	4.33	0.16	2.63	0.44	5.25	0.31
T ₁₃	2.83	0.31	4.15	0.16	2.95	0.35	5.05	0.32
T ₁₄	3.47	0.25	4.50	0.14	3.32	0.34	4.96	0.32
T ₁₅	2.82	0.32	4.38	0.13	2.63	0.40	4.82	0.32
T ₁₆	2.27	0.40	3.86	0.14	2.31	0.44	4.20	0.35
T ₁₇	1.93	0.46	2.46	0.22	2.04	0.48	3.62	0.38
T ₁₈	2.24	0.39	1.91	0.29	2.17	0.45	3.65	0.37
T ₁₉	2.18	0.37	2.25	0.23	2.04	0.44	3.40	0.40
T ₂₀	1.48	0.50	1.46	0.32	1.47	0.54	3.07	0.41
T ₂₁	1.22	0.56	1.63	0.24	1.35	0.57	2.63	0.46
T ₂₂	1.46	0.53	0.58	0.46	1.51	0.54	2.52	0.45
T ₂₃	-0.66	1.87	0.34	0.44	-0.24	1.44	1.89	0.51
T ₂₄	-0.10	1.12	0.02	0.54	0.26	0.98	1.59	0.57
T ₂₅	-0.03	1.25	0.94	0.28	0.19	1.14	1.32	0.64
T ₂₆	-0.16	0.37	0.63	0.16	0.26	0.32	1.14	0.27